

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D2.5

Final SWOT Analysis of WP2 Product Implementation

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 OBJECTIVES	9
1.2 TASKS	9
1.3 DELIVERABLES.....	10
1.4 GOALS	10
1.5 EXPECTED OUTCOMES.....	11
2 METHODS	11
3 RESULTS	12
3.1 TABLE OF WP2 TOOLS & RESOURCES	12
3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA STATISTICS & KEY FINDINGS.....	14
3.3 WEB EXPERIENCE STATISTICS & KEY FINDINGS.....	16
3.3.1 <i>Background and Development</i>	16
3.3.2 <i>Statistical Synopsis</i>	17
3.3.3 <i>Key Findings</i>	18
3.4 COMMUNICATION TOOLS & RESOURCES ASSESSMENT – KEY FINDINGS	18
3.4.1 <i>Summary of Key Findings</i>	19
3.4.2 <i>Web-Based Resources:</i>	19
3.4.3 <i>Meetings & Collaboration:</i>	21
3.4.4 <i>Strategic Tools:</i>	21
3.4.5 <i>Social Media Usage & Preferences:</i>	22
4 SWOT ANALYSIS	23
4.1 STRENGTHS	23
4.2 WEAKNESSES.....	24
4.3 OPPORTUNITIES	25
4.4 THREATS.....	26
5 RECOMMENDATIONS	28
6 CONCLUSION	31
7 ANNEX	32
7.1 MISSION OCEAN AND WATERS: SOCIAL MEDIA REPORT	33
7.2 MISSION OCEAN & WATERS: COMMUNICATION TOOLS & RESOURCES ASSESSMENT - FULL REPORT, INCLUDING INDIVIDUAL SURVEY RESPONSES	43

LISTS OF TABLES AND FIGURES

TABLE 1. TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS USED IN PREP4BLUE AND THE DOCUMENT.....	7
TABLE 2. TASKS, DELIVERABLES AND OTHER PRODUCTS AND SERVICES WP2 DEVELOPED AND IMPLEMENTED FROM 2022 TO 2025	12
IMAGE 1. PREP4BLUE AND WP2’S TARGET COLLABORATORS, USERS, AND AUDIENCES INCLUDED SEVERAL GROUPS SUCH AS CITIZENS, CSA COMMUNICATORS, PROJECT PARTNERS, THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY, AND MORE.	11
IMAGE 2. THIS TABLE ILLUSTRATES STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF THE SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS. IT CAN BE FOUND IN THE FULL SOCIAL MEDIA REPORT IN THE ANNEX.	15
IMAGE 3. THIS TABLE ILLUSTRATES OPPORTUNITIES AND THREATS AS THEY RELATED TO THE SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS. IT CAN BE FOUND IN THE FULL SOCIAL MEDIA REPORT IN THE ANNEX.	16
IMAGE 4. THESE IMAGES SHOW THE AVERAGE NUMBER OF VISITS PER MONTH, LOCATION OF VISITORS, AND OTHER STATISTICS RELATED TO THE WEB EXPERIENCE.....	17
IMAGE 5. HALF OF THE SURVEY TAKERS RATED THE TRELLO BOARD FAIRLY HIGH, WITH THE OTHER HALF EITHER NOT ANSWERING OR RATING IT MODERATE TO LOW.	19
IMAGE 6. 10 OUT OF 24 RESPONDENTS RATED THE WEB EXPERIENCE FAIRLY HIGH. THE OTHER 14 EITHER DIDN’T ANSWER OR RATED IT MODERATE TO LOW.	20
IMAGE 7. ALL RATINGS FOR THE DIGITAL ACADEMY WERE MODERATE TO LOW, ALTHOUGH IT APPEARS THIS IS DUE TO A NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS SAYING THEY NEVER ACCESSED IT OR COULDN’T ACCESS IT. 17 RESPONDENTS LEFT THE QUESTION BLANK	20
IMAGE 8. 15 OF THE 24 RESPONDENTS RATED THE COMMUNICATIONS COLLABORATIVE MEETINGS HIGH; 9 DIDN’T ANSWER.....	21
IMAGE 9. PROJECT PARTNERS PRIMARILY FOLLOW THE MISSION OCEAN AND WATERS LINKEDIN PAGE; USERS ARE INCREASINGLY LEAVING X, ALTHOUGH IT REMAINS THE PROJECT’S SECOND MOST POPULAR CHANNEL BY NUMBER OF FOLLOWERS.....	22
IMAGE 10. THE MISSION OCEAN AND WATERS “WEB EXPERIENCE” OFFERS USERS A DYNAMIC APPROACH TO LEARNING ABOUT THE MISSION.26	
IMAGE 11. THE TRELLO BOARD SERVES AS A CENTRAL REPOSITORY OF COMMUNICATIONS TOOLS AND RESOURCES FOR PROJECT PARTNERS.	27

Executive Summary

This final analysis of Work Package 2's (WP2) Product Implementation highlights strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) identified during the PREP4BLUE project. It also includes recommendations, social media statistics and findings from an internal project partner survey that assessed the usefulness of WP2's tools and resources. These findings demonstrate that the tasks and deliverables for the period have been met, and even exceeded, while also illustrating a need for further strategizing moving forward. This is especially true for products that require more structure, budget, resources, and legacy plans beyond PREP4BLUE's term in order to avoid losing tools instrumental to the success of the Mission and its partners, and to also better communicate the Mission in more streamlined and efficient ways.

Strengths:

- High engagement & reach: WP2's social media channels and campaigns achieved wide reach and engagement. As the conclusion of PREP4BLUE, the accounts had more than 9,500 followers collectively and had shared thousands of posts.
- Comprehensive communication strategy: Completion and publication of the Narrative Guide (D2.1), Communication Strategy (D2.2), dynamic Web Experience via missionoceanwaters.eu, Digital Academy, Digital Trello Board, PDF Toolkit, enhanced communications for both project partners and stakeholders as well as the public.
- Successful and robust collaborative networking: Proactive participation in numerous events, meetings, *etc.*, have bolstered the visibility of Mission initiatives and formed many successful relationships. The Communications Collaborative, in particular, has been very successful in ensuring project partners have the necessary contacts, tools, resources, and relationships to communicate effectively and as the EC wanted with respect to branding, imagery, tone, *etc.* Dozens of partners regularly attend these monthly meetings, with only as few as 50 and as many as 75 at one time. They are integral to information sharing among partners and represent a new way of “doing business” within the Mission.
- Dynamic and successful pilot initiative for future modelling via the “Mission Ocean and Waters Web-Experience”. More than a useful “website” for resources and information, the Web Experience fosters a sense of community and shared goals among users through unique and dynamic features such as drone video footage, hidden “easter eggs”, in-person interviews with Mission leaders and partners, thought-provoking facts and photographs, *etc.* Combined, they provide users a more experiential connection to the Mission and the waters in their lives versus the other more flat and textual webpages/websites devoted to the Mission.

Weaknesses:

- Complex processes created confusion: During the first half of the project, navigating EU interventions, particularly in branding, media, and events, required significant additional resources and time.
- Sustainability concerns highlight the lack of foresight into legacy and other planning by the EC as well as the ability of projects to finance such efforts: The long-term sustainability of platforms created for the Mission, *e.g.* social media channels, the Web Experience, *etc.* remain uncertain due to the funding and time-limited nature of CSAs, especially one like PREP4BLUE meant to create things that last and are useful.
- Content overlap and redundancy are wasteful, both financially and with respect to people's time: The establishment of the MIP (as a tender) and multiple web-based services and sites have resulted in confusion and redundancy, necessitating a strategic shift to focus on unique and engaging content

rather than duplicative efforts, which are an obvious problem (*e.g.*, EC already had a communications plan for the Missions but didn't use it, every new project creates another website, *etc.*).

- Costs often far exceeded what was anticipated due to inflation and other technical, practical, and operational challenges stemming from the use of new technologies and the complex Mission structures. As a result, as a “finished product” the Web Experience will likely never be updated (more than minor text fixes) beyond the PREP4BLUE closure due to costs.

Opportunities:

- Expansion of social media presence: There is significant potential to expand digital/paid campaigns, utilize platforms such as TikTok and BlueSky, and adapt new formats and multimedia storytelling to sustain audience engagement and enrich the Mission's narrative.
- Increased Collaboration: The relationships that have grown between the partner communications teams, including the MIP and EC, have the potential to help streamline future processes and improve the coherence of the Mission's branding and messaging as well as help with legacy plans and ensuring there is less duplication of products and services.
- The Web Experience could be substantially useful as a public face of the Mission, offering highlights of Mission contributions and by being complementary to other online sources. However, it will require more funding.

Threats:

- Regulatory and compliance Issues: The complexity of rules governing engagement between the EC, MIP, CSAs, and other projects could lead to challenges, especially in media and events.
- Potential loss of digital assets: Without future sustainability plans, assets and a strong online presence built during the project may be at risk once funding ends.
- Complexity and reach: It's getting too big for it not to have a real centralized and dynamic website that can direct users to all information on the Mission while also inspiring the public. Without a real campaign aimed at reaching the public, such as through viable media (Netflix, *etc.*) and very large events, the opportunities for public engagement are limited to the echo chamber. Right now, all events seem to be very stakeholder focused rather than public focused, and given the projects' tasks, this likely won't change.

Final Recommendations:

- Have a dedicated and centralized communications/PR team or project with an adequate budget and accessible resources specifically for reaching the broader public rather, including planning large-scale events. It's unreasonable to believe small projects can plan large-scale events to impact large swaths of the public when they have a number of other tasks and deliverables to meet.
- Require mandatory attendance and participation in the Communications Collaborative meetings for all project partners.
- Select at least two social media channels that all projects must use daily for consistent communication across “official” channels for the Mission and move social media responsibilities for the Mission to the dedicated PR team.
- Only have one centralized website for everything, including the projects.
- The MIP, or other such entity, is integral to facilitating collaboration and information sharing between projects and the EC, and it must continue to exist as long as there are legal, regulatory, and compliance issues in dealing directly with the EC.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
P4B	PREP4BLUE
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
the Mission	Mission Ocean and Waters
DX.X	Deliverable (by number)
WP2	Work Package 2 (within PREP4BLUE)
MIP	Mission Implementation Platform
EC	European Commission
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
KDM	Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung
O	Objective (by number as noted in the grant agreement)
DTI	Digital Training Institute

1 Introduction

PREP4BLUE Work Package 2 (WP2), Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communications & Spaces, was led by KDM and focused on communicating the Mission. Through the creation of various print, digital, and web-based tools, WP2 aimed to build on and connect the many existing projects and initiatives at the EU, national, and local levels, as well as inspire awe and wonder around the ocean - connecting people with things they deeply value and welcome – and eliciting interest in taking action.

WP2's original objectives, tasks, and deliverables from the grant agreement are noted below. However, as is the case often with CSAs who are unaware of activities happening prior to funding and by other institutions, such as the EC, WP2's objectives, tasks, and deliverables were adjusted post-funding to meet the new demands and situational aspects and expectations of the project. For example, while we noted we would create the branding, the EC had already done that prior to our funding so our focus shifted from developing to promoting the branding for consistent use across the projects. Additionally, to avoid duplicating other content and confusion with other websites, we rebranded and altered our strategy for our "website", missionoceanwaters.eu, so that people have a much more engaging "Web Experience" rather than land on a "portal" for general information. Refer to D2.3 *"Report on virtual space pilot and website including overview of existing Mission contributions and spaces for Mission-related events"* for more information on adjustments made to WP2's work post-funding and after multiple discussions with the EC, MIP, and other partners.

Mid-way through the project, WP2 completed D2.4, the Interim SWOT Analysis, to better gauge where we were in our work, what was successful versus what could be improved, and how best to move forward. This report is WP2's final SWOT analysis and recommendations (D2.5) and highlights WP2's final conclusions on the project work, including, but not limited to, our tasks and deliverables.

- The Methods section describes our approach to compiling the information for this report.
- The Results sections includes a complete list of tasks and deliverables completed and other tools and resources produced and provided. The Results section also includes key social media and Web Experience statistics as well as main findings from the Communication Tools & Resources Assessment.
- The SWOT Analysis section delves into the details of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats identified.
- The Recommendations section offers advice for the EC based on our "boots-on-the-ground" experience in communicating the Mission over the past three years.
- Our Conclusion section extrapolates from all of the information compiled to articulate our final impressions.
- Finally, Annex 7.1 contains the full *Final Mission Ocean and Waters Social Media Report*, and Annex 7.2 the *Communication and Tools & Resources Assessment Report*.

We hope this final SWOT analysis aids the Mission in fine-tuning communications for this very important initiative, allowing for better service to the project partners while also increasing public reach to foster increased engagement in protecting our ocean and waters.

1.1 Objectives

- **O1:** Develop a strong Mission Narrative as a means of realising a transformative and systemic portfolio approach to support the Mission and its activities
- **O2:** Prepare an overarching Mission Communication Strategy by providing key messaging and visionary visual examples based on the best available science and innovation, tailor-made for various audiences, and including social, digital, and traditional media
- **O3:** Support preparation of the Mission Implementation Platform and its Forum by designing and piloting innovative physical and virtual Mission Spaces for the Mission community and general population

1.2 Tasks

- **Task 2.1 – Develop Mission Narrative Guide** (Duration: M1-M6): Based on the work of the Mission Board and legal texts, the aim is to produce a Mission Narrative Guide (D2.1) to help (i) Mission contributors understand the larger effort they are part of and (ii) make the Mission’s relevance intuitively clear to European citizens, regardless of age, education, gender, ethnicity or background. WP2 will host at least two workshops/interactive events (in different LH Basins) specifically targeting the Mission contributors (internal), but with activities open to all interested parties - the first one ideally taking place early in the project in conjunction with a visible event (*e.g.*, during the French EU Council Presidency). Moderated by professional media and social science experts, and including designers, artists, activists, etc., the workshops will support the development of guidelines with the main Mission slogan/motto, key messaging regarding what the Mission actually is, and key concepts, definitions, and ideas (in line with official Mission documents). We will draw on perception surveys (*e.g.*, on emotional disconnect) and work with other initiatives, notably the European Bauhaus, to ensure a unified narrative. We will implement a testing phase using other WPs and citizen engagement (T3.4) confirming assess effectiveness of messages for different audiences. Results will be used to fine-tune the Narrative Guide elements for use in the overarching Mission Communication Strategy.
- **Task 2.2 – Develop Overarching Communication Strategy** (Duration: M1-M9): Working with the EC, and the Mission implementation platform, T2.2 will prepare the overarching Mission Communication Strategy (D2.2), including branding elements such as the corporate design for the mission, Narrative Guide elements, and incorporating social/digital media. The work will be structured in the following steps: scoping, research (*e.g.*, mapping perceptions and types of mission contributions), analysis, and pilot test. A branding guidebook with multimedia elements will be produced; subsequent deliverables could include subchapters for replicability to use across future networks. It will propose inspirational and emblematic science and innovation-based images and messages to aid Mission communication goals, including visualizing the narrative (T2.1).
- **Task 2.3 – Narrative & Strategy Testing Through Pilot Campaigns & Spaces** (Duration: M1-M36): T2.3 will pilot the narrative and Communications Strategy through a social media campaign, virtual spaces, and intergenerational and inclusive physical spaces as venues for meetings, interactions, exhibitions, etc., to engage Mission contributors and citizens across Europe. The task will organise at least two exhibitions/public events in iconic spaces (*e.g.*, Ocean Space | Venice) with artists, designers, architects, the European Bauhaus, and other initiatives to showcase the Mission and its contributors. These products will be positioned as globally-visible contributions to the UN Ocean Decade.

- *Subtask 2.3.1: Pilot a social media campaign, including public competitions, aimed at bringing Mission information to young people.* The Terms of Reference will be part of the Communication Strategy. This task will draw on and coordinate with T3.4 and other campaigns across Europe to engage citizens.
- *Subtask 2.3.2: Conceptualize, design, and pilot an interactive, multidimensional virtual Mission space (website), including an overview of all Mission contributions and Mission-related events.* During the coronavirus pandemic, online venue technology has increased dramatically. This task will include working with online venue developers to explore the most advanced, open-source, accessible (CMS) software available and develop a virtual space pilot. This space will include a lobby, information booth, several auditoriums, cinema, exhibition hall, social media wall, etc., and ideally serve as a model, or the actual website, for the duration of the Mission. Working with WP4 WP6 and others, this task will showcase progress in Mission implementation (e.g., a Progress Dashboard and Map), including, where possible, increased restoration efforts and their impact on communities. It is intended be used by both the public and mission community with public and private (log-in) spaces featuring tools and information to aid both. We will work with other EU Missions (e.g., cities), living labs, citizen initiatives, etc. in order ensure inclusivity.
- *Subtask 2.3.3: Conceptualise, design, and pilot with potential venues (e.g., museums and aquaria) from around the world physical Mission spaces that serve to exhibit Mission contributions and as venues to hold Mission-related activities (e.g., citizen assemblies, foresight workshops, future labs, etc.) in Europe.* The budget for implementing this subtask will be allocated when the Terms of Reference have been finalized. A close cooperation/co-location with WP3 is foreseen.

1.3 Deliverables

- D2.1 – Mission Narrative Guide : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944249>
- D2.2 – Communication Strategy and the Terms of Reference for the virtual and physical spaces : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944489>
- D2.3 – Report on virtual space pilot and website including overview of existing Mission contributions and spaces for Mission-related events : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944310>
- D2.4 – Interim SWOT analysis of WP product implementation : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14872534>
- **D2.5 – Final SWOT analysis of WP product implementation (this document)**

1.4 Goals

- Create inspiring and accessible platforms for communicating the Mission
- Increase stakeholder and citizen awareness about, and engagement with, the Mission
- Promote the Lighthouses and their contributions (show the successes, highlight the impacts, encourage mobilization, and convey the principles/values of why we're doing this)
- Advocate for and assist with consistency in messaging/branding across Mission partners
- Provide helpful tools, information, and support in Mission communication activities.

1.5 Expected Outcomes

We believed that if we met our goals, we would achieve the following outcomes:

- There is increased access to Mission information and therefore an actual increase in understanding of, and engagement with, the Mission.
- PREP4BLUE partners, other CSAs, and Mission-related initiatives have and use the proper branding/messaging tools for instant recognizability and Mission cohesion.
- Stories that champion the Mission are published and circulated outside “echo chambers” for broader public appreciation, understanding, and engagement.
- Mission contributors and partners understand the larger effort they are part of and can more efficiently collaborate as well as articulate their work across audiences.

Image 1. PREP4BLUE and WP2’s target collaborators, users, and audiences included several groups such as citizens, CSA communicators, project partners, the scientific community, and more.

2 Methods

WP2 used a variety of methods to complete this SWOT analysis and develop recommendations for the future of Mission Ocean and Waters as it relates to communications. These included:

- With the assistance of WP2’s social media contractor (Joanne Sweeney of the Digital Training Institute [DTI]), WP2 compiled statistics from the social media channels, Digital Academy, and Trello Board.
- With the assistance of Kubik Photo (the contractor for the creation of the Web Experience), WP2 compiled statistics for the Web Experience (missionoceanwaters.eu).
- WP2 conducted a survey (Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment) of Mission Ocean and Waters partners who attend the Communications Collaborative meetings to gather opinions of the PREP4BLUE WP2 tools and resources provided.
- WP2 referred to other activities, documents, conversations, feedback, events, *etc.* from the past three years to assess products, activities, and efforts completed in support of communication of the Mission.

3 Results

WP2 completed all tasks and deliverables, created and implemented various other helpful tools and resources, and attended multiple events - most of which were outside of the original scope of expected work. Collectively, these activities resulted in several mini-campaigns on social media as well as relationship building that fostered increased information sharing and a stronger sense of community among partners. It is WP2's belief that throughout the project, these expanded communications products and activities aided and promoted the Mission and stakeholders in the community by ensuring access to important information along with a sense of belonging.

3.1 Table of WP2 Tools & Resources

A list of WP2's outputs with descriptions and links to the item are in the table below. The majority of the items noted can also be found on the Trello Board at <https://trello.com/b/Q2SEkYw/missionocean-social-media-toolkit>.

Table 2. Tasks, deliverables and other products and services WP2 developed and implemented from 2022 to 2025

WP2 Tools & Resources - Descriptions & Links	
<p>✓ Narrative Guide (T2.1 & D2.1) https://trello.com/c/UrcREakR and doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944248</p>	<p>This guide was developed to facilitate storytelling about the Mission, fostering a sense of connection and empathy among the public. It was posted on the Trello Board for all partners to utilize in their media work, promoted in meetings, and elements are incorporated into the Web Experience and referenced in the Communication Strategy, which was also provided to all partners via the Trello Board.</p>
<p>✓ Communication Strategy (T2.2 and D2.2) https://trello.com/c/qcAyfDss and doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944488</p>	<p>A cohesive communication strategy was devised to ensure consistent branding and enhance public recognition of the Mission. It's on the Trello Board for all partners to utilize in their media work.</p>
<p>✓ Report On Virtual Space Pilot and Website Including Overview of Existing Mission Contributions and Spaces for Mission-Related Events (D2.3) https://zenodo.org/records/10944310</p>	<p>This report summarized the development and implementation of the Web Experience and our events approximately half-way through the project.</p>
<p>✓ Interim SWOT Analysis of WP Product Implementation (D2.4) https://zenodo.org/records/14872535</p>	<p>Developed mid-term, this report summarized the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the development, implementation, and dissemination of WP2's products and services. The analysis was used to ensure the last half of the project remained in line with our goals and objectives.</p>
<p>✓ Final SWOT Analysis of WP Product Implementation (D2.5) (this document)</p>	<p>This final deliverable report summarizes the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the development, implementation, and dissemination of WP2's products and services. More comprehensive than D2.4, it also includes two other reports WP2 produced that were used to make this final assessment; these reports collected data and feedback on social media and WP2's tools and resources effectiveness. Data on the Web Experience was also collected. D2.5 also makes a number of recommendations based on the SWOT for the EC to consider as the Mission continues and evolves without PREP4BLUE.</p>

✓ **Web Experience (Subtask 2.3.2) [Missionoceanwaters.eu](https://missionoceanwaters.eu)**

Designed to complement the EC’s Mission webpage, this Web Experience features testimonials, interviews, and visually compelling content to capture the public’s attention and engagement by showcasing Mission Lighthouses and individual contributions through immersive scenes. It’s featured on the “One-Stop Shop Portal” accessed via the EC’s Mission Ocean and Waters webpage.

✓ **Social Media Channels (Task 2.2) & Campaigns (Subtask 2.3.1)**

Seven social media channels were created and four are regularly utilised to disseminate calls-to-action, event updates, videos, photos, and relevant information tailored to the target audience, including specialised campaigns. Several social media campaigns were held, including Lighthouse and other events to promote the Mission (often at the EC’s request) as well as our own “Generation Blue” campaign featuring original content from four mobile journalists (MoJos) to engage youth and change up the narrative for enhanced citizen engagement. Collectively, WP2 travelled to approximately 15 events across Europe to publicize the Mission live on social media. Partners were encouraged to email WP2 and the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP) with content they wanted published. The MIP has assumed a contributory role in posting on the channels (at the EC’s request), and part of the legacy plan is for them, or another tender or the EC, to take over the majority of posting when PREP4BLUE sunsets. A legacy plan was sent to PREP4BLUE’s project officer for consideration in consultation with the EC and MIP.

Channels include:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/missionoceanu>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/ourmissionocean>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/missionocean/>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/missionoceanu/>
- TikTok: <https://www.tiktok.com/missionoceanwaters>
- Pinterest: <http://pinterest.com/missionoceanwaters/>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8Zjl1TyDAUuDO8QNLnd9zw>

✓ **STARTS4WATER ARTS RESIDENCY & EXHIBITION (Subtask 2.3.3) <https://starts.eu/what-we-do/lighthouses-2/>**

WP2 collaborated with the STARTS4WATER project (Grant agreement ID: 101059372) to co-host and co-organize public events, exhibitions, etc. STARTS4WATER has an arts focus and WP2 collaborated to select artists-in-residence, provide a link between scientists and artists, and ultimately support the START4WATERS’ focus on the Mission Ocean and Waters goals.

✓ **V.ECOP Days 2024, 2025 (Subtask 2.3.3) <https://Vecop.net>**

The Virtual Early Career Ocean Professional (V.ECOP) Days are a unique livestream event series showcasing testimonies of change in applying science and knowledge to ocean sustainability from the global community of ECOPs. Hosted by and for ECOPs as a contribution to the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, on-site ECOP mobile journalists provided live coverage to showcase commitments to both the Decade and the Mission in Barcelona in 2024. This hybrid event attracted over 400 participants and over 100 live programme contributions from Europe and around the world. V.ECOP Days 2025 is planned for Nice in June 2025 as part of the third UN Ocean Conference. Therefore, reporting on it for this report is not possible, but WP2 staff are involved in ensuring the event promotes the Mission.

✓ **“Communications Collaborative” Working Group (Bonus)**

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TU-o99gU_xxk1ALE4ggmn1z-ne4eGjff_fOvhU-yeI/edit?tab=t.0

This platform facilitates collaboration among Mission communication partners as described above. While started by WP2, the group was eventually handed over to the MIP to avoid duplicative efforts. It has continued to grow over the three years of the PREP4BLUE project, and 50-75 participants regularly attend the monthly meetings. Partners are invited by the MIP to join the group during their onboarding to the Mission and can also email MIP Communication at mip-communication@technopolis-group.com for more information.

✓ **Trello Board (Bonus)** <https://bit.ly/MissionOceanSocialMedia>

A comprehensive Trello Board (Trello.com is an online tool for sharing resources) serves as a centralised repository of communication information, tools, resources, and links related to the Mission, facilitating accessibility and dissemination of information to the partners and public. To ensure the content isn’t lost, the MIP is working on migrating the content to their platforms.

✓ **PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit (Bonus)** <https://trello.com/c/Adz09TaT>

This toolkit, available in PDF format, was produced at the EC’s request to complement the Trello Board. It serves as a resource for new projects, equipping them with the necessary information and materials to promote the Mission effectively. It is available on the Trello Board and also emailed to new partners by the MIP during onboarding.

✓ **Mission Ocean & Waters Digital Academy (Bonus)** <https://bit.ly/MissionOceanSocialMedia>

Previously an exclusive platform for project partners and charter signatories, the Academy was established to provide special communication tools and training on utilizing social media. The goal was to help the partners and signatories learn how to properly promote the Mission and their respective roles within it. While it was advertised as a bonus for Charter signatories and partners only, the content from the Academy was moved from its old platform to the publicly available Trello Board in March 2025 so the content isn’t lost when PREP4BLUE ends in May 2025. The MIP is now working on moving the content to their platforms.

✓ **Events, Activities, & Meetings Attended to Foster Collaboration and Promote the Mission via Social Media (Bonus)**

WP2 staff attended in person approximately 15 Mission Ocean and Waters events, activities, or large meetings; these included all 3 Mission Ocean and Waters Forums, PREP4BLUE Annual Meetings, and Lighthouse or other related events in Marseille, Nice, Palermo, Gothenburg, Hamburg, Brussels, Barcelona, Brest, Genoa, Venice, Ravenna, Cork, Lisbon, and more. All events were promoted on social media channels via mini campaigns and can be viewed in past posts.

3.2 Social Media Statistics & Key Findings

DTI completed a final analysis of our Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels. DTI was instrumental in the social media channels’ development during the first year of the project, including running the Generation Blue campaign (more information on the Generation Blue Social Media Campaign can be found in D2.4). A synopsis of key findings is below. Refer to the Annex 7.1 for the full Mission Ocean and Waters Social Media Report.

Key Findings:

Between June 2022 and May 2025, the Mission Ocean social media channels established a strong digital presence across six platforms: Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, X, YouTube and TikTok publishing over 2,000 posts and generating more than 20,000 engagements and 2.2 million impressions. We experimented with a seventh channel, Pinterest, but it didn't deliver a return and the results were negligible. The social media strategy successfully tailored content for diverse audiences, from EU citizens and youth to policymakers and scientific communities. Instagram and X were the most active and engaging channels initially, however, LinkedIn emerged as the most effective for professional and policy-related reach, especially in the final year. TikTok showed promise for storytelling but struggled with audience growth as human-led content works best there and WP2 had limited access to video content. Strategic content such as original Lighthouse-specific case studies, event coverage, Horizon EU project features, and explainer content performed best, while partnerships with HorizonEU, European Commission accounts, and NGOs amplified visibility. Insights from this final report provide valuable lessons on content planning, influencer activation, and platform prioritisation that can inform future EU mission communications.

SWOT Analysis

|
Weaknesses |
|--|--|
| Limited audience growth on Facebook and TikTok |
| TikTok failed to develop a follower base |
| Facebook engagement plateaued despite high volume of posts |
| LinkedIn underutilised in 2022–2023; most traction in final year |
| Reducing X reach and engagement |

Image 2. This table illustrates strengths and weaknesses of the social media platforms. It can be found in the full social media report in the Annex.

SWOT Analysis

|
Threats |
|--|---|
| Platform algorithm changes reducing organic visibility |
| Limited internal resources to support content planning and video production |
| Audience fragmentation may require narrower targeting and paid boosts |
| Potential cuts to communications budgets post-project phase |
| Reputational risk on X right now |

Image 3. This table illustrates opportunities and threats as they related to the social media platforms. It can be found in the full social media report in the Annex.

3.3 Web Experience Statistics & Key Findings

3.3.1 Background and Development

Subtask 2.3.2., entitled Virtual Mission Space (Website / Dashboard) Conceptualize, design, and pilot an interactive, multidimensional virtual Mission space, set out to present an overview of all Mission contributions and Mission-related events. During the coronavirus pandemic, online venue technology has increased dramatically. This task aimed to work with online venue developers to explore the most advanced, open-source, accessible (CMS) software available and develop a virtual space pilot. This space was intended to include a lobby, information booth, several auditoriums, cinema, exhibition hall, social media wall, etc., and ideally serve as a model, or the actual website, for the duration of the Mission. Working with WP4, WP6 and others, this task will showcase progress in Mission implementation (e.g., a Progress Dashboard and Map), including, where possible, increased restoration efforts and their impact on communities. It is intended be used by both the public and mission community with public and private (log-in) spaces featuring tools and information to aid both. The task will work with other EU Missions (e.g., cities), living labs, citizen initiatives, etc. in order ensure inclusivity.

Early in Prep4Blue a Concept was articulated and a test site created. The concept and a test site were presented at the Prep4Blue Annual General Meeting in 2023, incorporating participant feedback documented in Annex 1. Subsequently, a revised draft of the website was completed in mid-November 2023, and next steps include completing website content design and structure, translation, and filming specific sub-pages at scheduled events in April and May 2024. An official launch event is planned, ideally coinciding with established events like the European Maritime Day or a Mission Forum. Due to a number of developments, such as the creation of WaveLinks by other Prep4Blue partners, meant that the proposal for the website was reevaluated and, ultimately, an immersive web experience was developed and is now located at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu> as well as on the EU Mission Ocean and Waters homepage.

The immersive web experience set out to effectively communicate the Mission's diversity and dynamism. It does offer a unique contribution to showcasing the Mission and to fostering community engagement as a contribution to implementing the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030. At the same time, it faces challenges in adjusting due to the inherent nature of websites. Multilingualism emerged as a particular challenge, requiring custom-developed solutions for translation due to the varied language preferences of speakers. The site is now available in 5 languages. Designing and constructing the website proved more complex than anticipated, with ongoing efforts to perfect it likely lasting until the end of the Prep4Blue project.

3.3.2 Statistical Synopsis

Image 4. These images show the average number of visits per month, location of visitors, and other statistics related to the Web Experience.

3.3.3 Key Findings

Strengths

1. **Engagement and Interaction:** The “Mission Ocean and Waters Web-Experience” features interactive pages designed to enhance user engagement by showcasing Mission Lighthouses and individual contributions through immersive scenes.
2. **Community Building:** The narrative structure of the web experience, organized around "My Mission, Our Mission, and EU Mission," effectively fosters a sense of community and shared goals among users.
3. **Comprehensive Content:** The web experience includes numerous testimonials, contributions from various EU projects, and references many initiatives, making it a useful resource for information related to the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

Weaknesses

1. **Technical Challenges:** The web experience development faced significant delays due to the need for filming in conjunction with Mission events and reprogramming to improve navigation. Adjustments to the web experience are costly and time-consuming as they require programming work.

Opportunities

1. **Public Visibility:** There is an opportunity to make the web experience the public face of the Mission, offering highlights of the contributions towards the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.
2. **Complementarity and Added Value:** By ensuring the web experience complements existing Mission services (like the European Commission website and various Mission project website), the web experience can enhance its value and visibility.

Threats

1. **Sustainability of Updates:** The ongoing need for programming work to make adjustments could strain resources and delay future updates, affecting the web experience's long-term sustainability and relevance.
2. **Multilingualism Challenges:** The complexity of providing content in multiple languages, especially when speakers prefer or insist on English, poses a significant challenge to effective communication and engagement.
3. **Technological Dependencies:** Dependence on specific technologies and service providers for web experience functionality and filming might introduce vulnerabilities and affect the web experience's stability and performance.

3.4 Communication Tools & Resources Assessment – Key Findings

The [“Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment” survey](#) was conducted among the Mission Ocean & Waters Communications Collaborative members. The purpose of the survey was to assess the value of the communication tools and resources WP2 developed or provided that were meant to help partners in communicating the Mission and their project's role within it while adhering to brand guidelines. The survey was open from March through April 2025, and 24 responses were received. A brief synopsis of the key findings is below. Refer to the Annex 7.2 for the full survey report, including copies of the 24 individual responses.

3.4.1 Summary of Key Findings

The Mission Ocean and Waters communications tools and resources were generally well received by the 24 survey respondents, though many questions were left blank, making it difficult to ascertain true opinions on certain products from all project partner members of the group. Responses to open-ended questions demonstrated that while the tools and resources were viewed as useful overall, the main challenges were awareness gaps, onboarding inconsistencies, and occasional technical or navigational issues. Participants emphasized the strategic value of communication platforms in enhancing Mission visibility and coordination. Improving promotion and access to these resources—and strengthening the support for social media amplification—would enhance their impact moving forward. This is part of the reason WP2 recommends creating one centralized website for all projects, partners, and information as well as establishing mandatory/main social media platforms.

General findings include:

- Web-Based Resources
- Meetings & Collaboration
- Strategic Tools
- Social Media Usage & Preferences:

3.4.2 Web-Based Resources:

- **Trello Board (Social Media Toolkit):** Most respondents were aware of and had used the Trello Board, finding it valuable for accessing branded content and staying updated. However, a few found its layout overwhelming or had not had time to explore it fully. It was visited more than 1200 times using the tracking link; however there were other links users could have used, meaning it could have been visited even more.

Image 5. Half of the survey takers rated the Trello board fairly high, with the other half either not answering or rating it moderate to low.

- **Mission Web Experience (missionoceanwaters.eu):** Feedback on the site’s design was mostly positive, with users appreciating the creative and immersive aspects. However, there were reports of usability issues, bugs, and slow performance - limiting its effectiveness.

Image 6. 10 out of 24 respondents rated the Web Experience fairly high. The other 14 either didn’t answer or rated it moderate to low.

- **Digital Academy:** Some users had trouble accessing the platform or were unaware of it altogether. 17 respondents opted not to rate it. Those who did access it found it average to below-average. This suggests that it may not have been worth the effort. However, based on usage statistics, 468 people registered to use it and on average watched two videos.

Image 7. All ratings for the Digital Academy were moderate to low, although it appears this is due to a number of respondents saying they never accessed it or couldn’t access it. 17 respondents left the question blank

3.4.3 Meetings & Collaboration:

- **Communications Collaborative Working Group Meetings:** These were generally viewed as very beneficial, particularly for staying informed and collaborating across projects. Only a few respondents were unaware of the meetings, and this illustrates how important consistent outreach during onboarding is. Respondents appreciated updates from the European Commission and opportunities for networking and synergy among projects. 15 out of 24 respondents rated them highly. The other 9 didn't respond. There were no negative ratings, suggesting this is one of the most effective tools at the Mission's disposal.

Image 8. 15 of the 24 respondents rated the Communications Collaborative meetings high; 9 didn't answer.

There were no low ratings for the meetings, and comments consistently reflected how important having access to the EC was during the meetings. This demonstrates their incredible value to those involved with communications for the projects.

3.4.4 Strategic Tools:

- Tools like the **Narrative Guide**, **Communication Strategy**, and **PREP4BLUE Toolkit** were sometimes read and rated positively, although some participants were unaware of their existence or had not engaged with them.
- Lack of knowledge about the **CIRCABC Group** (managed by the EC and used to access official media resources not available on the Trello board) was common. This platform is not managed by WP2.

3.4.5 Social Media Usage & Preferences:

- **LinkedIn** emerged as the most useful platform for professional engagement and updates among partners in the group. **Twitter/X** drew mixed reactions, with some supporting its removal and others still using it; it remains the platform with our second largest group of followers amongst partners. There was support for a BlueSky account.
- There was limited to moderate awareness of the **Generation Blue** and **V.ECOP Days 24** campaigns. Participants appreciated youth engagement but felt more project-centered amplification was needed. These results may also be due in part to some of the respondents having started their projects after these events took place.

Image 9. Project Partners primarily follow the Mission Ocean and Waters LinkedIn page; users are increasingly leaving X, although it remains the project's second most popular channel by number of followers.

4 SWOT Analysis

Using the information contained in the various reports, personal analysis of the work involved and completed, and evaluation of experiences at events, in meetings, and through correspondence, WP2 posits the following with respect to the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with Mission communications work.

4.1 Strengths

- **Achievement of Original Goals:** Successfully completed all planned tasks and deliverables including the Narrative Guide (D2.1), Communication Strategy (D2.2), Web Experience (Subtask 2.3.2), social media campaign (Subtask 2.3.1), innovative event (Subtask 2.3.3), social media channels (Task 2.2), *etc.*
- **Exceeded Expectations with Additional Tools, Products, and Services :** Delivered additional helpful outputs such as several mini social media campaigns, two comprehensive Communication Toolkits (one digital via the Trello Board and one in PDF form), a Digital Academy for partners and those who endorsed the Charter, attended several more events than anticipated/expected, and promoted hundreds of events and projects on social media, and created the Communications Collaborative group – all beyond the initial scope of the grant agreement.
- **Collaborative Networking Continues to Expand Thanks to Our Working Group:** Established a robust Communications Collaborative Working Group and regularly conducted and/or attended monthly meetings involving diverse stakeholders, enhancing collaboration and information sharing. The synergy created through the working group boosted the outreach and impact of the Mission’s messages, fostering a unified voice and approach and leading to improved communication effectiveness across the board. The group meets monthly and approximately 50-80 people regularly attend. It continues to grow as new partners are added and remains an integral part of ensuring branding is on point and the EC is informed/involved.
- **Visible and Robust Attendance & Engagement Has Led to Successful Relationships:** WP2 has been proactive in participating in numerous events, significantly enhancing the visibility and engagement of Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives. Such networking through regular meetings and events contributed also to the visibility and engagement of the Mission initiatives. This participation was well beyond the initial scope and instrumental in growing the Mission Ocean & Waters audience and engagement. The team's involvement in various EC-requested events demonstrated their commitment and adaptability.
- **Effective Social Media Campaigns and Regular Social Media Posting Have Grown Our Following & Engagement:** Collectively across all seven social media channels, we’ve had extensive reach and have organically grown from 0 to more than 9,500 followers, with approximately half of those on LinkedIn, the emerging platform in these polarizing times for social media. Additionally, the social media campaigns achieved high engagement and reach with significant growth in followers and impressions across platforms. For instance, the Generation Blue campaign achieved 2.84 million impressions and high engagement across Facebook and Instagram. This approach increased engagement through fresher and more relatable content and brought additional narratives to the audience. It was specifically targeted at ECOPs and the younger generations, also an increasingly popular target audience for the EC.

- Breakdown of Generation Blue campaign (refer to the full campaign report in the Annex of D2.4)
 - 732 social media posts published across all platforms over two weeks
 - Cumulative reach of 31.2K from TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram
 - 2.84 million total impressions from LinkedIn, Instagram, and Facebook
 - 2 million hashtag impacts/impressions from #GenerationBlue and #MissionOcean
- **Web-Experience:** The Web Experience features interactive pages designed to enhance user engagement by showcasing Mission Lighthouses and individual contributions through immersive scenes leading to a more dynamic user experience. The narrative structure of the Web Experience organized around "My Mission, Our Mission, and EU Mission," effectively fosters a sense of community and shared goals among users. It also includes numerous testimonials, contributions from various EU projects, and references many initiatives, making it a useful resource for information related to the Mission.

4.2 Weaknesses

- **Sustainability & Legacy Concerns:** There are potential sustainability issues for the digital platforms (Web Experience , social media channels, Digital Academy, Trello Board, *etc.*) given the time and funding-limited nature of CSAs as well as the EC's rules on social media channels and the related complications in establishing a long-term plan for such platforms. The sustainability of the digital platforms created for the Mission was uncertain for many months until WP2 and the MIP worked together to come up with a legacy plan. The intricacies of working out a long-term plan raised concerns about maintaining and possibly even losing these assets as well as continuing the engagement efforts once the initial funding ceases. This is something the EC needs to address in future projects.
- **Complex EC Rules, Processes, and Expectations:** Challenges in navigating and complying with the European Commission's complex, and even contradictory, rules for branding and communications sometimes hampered effective collaboration, especially with partners who sought answers to their questions specifically on branding and communications but received mixed or even negative responses. Responses from the EC sometimes caused delays and confusion, hindering smooth operations. Additionally, the EC often misinterpreted our role as a CSA rather than a tender and often made requests that were well beyond the scope of our work and that of partners, for example, requesting that we attend so many events to cover on social media, or to create a PDF of the Trello Board to serve as a toolkit (neither were part of tasks/deliverables). These complexities, additional requests, *etc.* required additional time and resources on our part, impacting overall efficiency and morale.
- **Overlapping Tasks/Content & Redundancy:** Multiple web-based services and sites led to confusion and potential for redundancy, requiring a shift in focus while partners made an effort to discern who was responsible for doing what and how. For example, this led WP2 to emphasize more engaging and unique content on our Web Experience , missionoceanwaters.eu. Additionally, the overlap between WP2 tasks and the MIP's tasks necessitated continuous coordination to avoid redundancy and ensure efficient resource use. For example, the MIP was officially tasked with creating a communications group, which we had already done. Rather than having two, the MIP assumed management of ours, the "Communications Collaborative". While WP2 and the MIP were able to work together very well and didn't encounter many problems, it looks as though the EC has segregated departments that aren't speaking with each other when developing project calls versus tender calls, especially as it relates to expected outcomes, deliverables, *etc.*

- **Some tools and resources weren't as widely used or valued as assumed:** The survey results demonstrate that some things, like the Digital Academy, weren't as widely known or used as assumed. Newer projects onboarding in the past year also don't appear to be aware of initial products developed to help them, such as the Narrative Guide, Communication Strategy, etc. This demonstrates that it's important to assess which tools are valuable to the actual projects and move forward with ones that are while potentially dropping ones that aren't.
- **Web-Experience:** The Web Experience development faced significant delays due to the development of multiple online platforms by different Mission related actors, the need for filming in conjunction with Mission events and reprogramming to improve navigation. Feedback indicated some difficulties with navigation, loading times, and browser compatibility. User engagement continues to grow but does not reach the public in the ways expected.

4.3 Opportunities

- **Expansion of Social Media Presence:** Continued growth and engagement on social media platforms can further enhance the project's visibility and impact. There is potential to expand digital campaigns leveraging the strong engagement metrics and broad reach achieved. Plans for future campaigns, including a paid campaign in collaboration with MIP/EC, can further amplify impact. Further engaging youth and communities through targeted, but not necessarily paid, campaigns and storytelling can foster greater public interest and involvement, although this must be balanced with also promoting the projects.
- **Leveraging Networks:** The established collaborative networks can be leveraged to support more comprehensive and integrated communication strategies, increasing the project's reach and influence.
- **Innovative Content Formats:** Opportunity to explore new content formats and multimedia storytelling can keep the audience engaged. Continuing to document and share unique, impactful stories from contributors can enhance the Mission's narrative and content library – as well as add to any future large-scale events or productions.
- **Increased Collaboration with EC:** Strengthening the working relationship with the EC's communications teams and project officers could help streamline processes and enhance the coherence of the Mission's branding and messaging. This collaboration can lead to more efficient use of resources and better alignment with broader EU objectives. It can also help alleviate duplication of work.
- **Web-Experience:** The Web Experience provides the only online tool to showcase what the different Mission funded projects are doing to implement the Mission. There is an opportunity to make the Web Experience the public face of the Mission, offering highlights of the contributions towards the Mission. By ensuring the Web Experience complements existing Mission services (like the European Commission website and various Mission project websites), the Web Experience can enhance its value and visibility.

Image 10. The Mission Ocean and Waters “Web Experience” offers users a dynamic approach to learning about the Mission. As a “pilot”, it serves as a unique example of how future websites could be better developed to reach the public with other options besides heavy content and flat text.

4.4 Threats

- **Long-term Sustainability/Loss of Assets:** Without a long-term sustainability plan for the digital platforms, there is a risk that these valuable resources may be lost post-project and other projects waste time and money “reinventing the wheel”. Ensuring the continuity of these platforms is crucial. Without a sustainable plan, there is a risk of losing the digital assets and the robust online presence built during the project once funding ends. While a social media legacy plan was sent to the EC, at the time of writing this report, there was no formal response to it. WP2 is moving forward with the MIP to do what it is possible to ensure assets aren’t lost.
- **Coordination Challenges:** The need for continuous coordination to manage overlapping tasks and ensure alignment with the EC, MIP, and numerous other partners strains resources and operational efficiency. Without the Communications Collaborative and the MIP, this would have been a disaster. Such things need to be addressed for future projects.
- **Regulatory and Compliance Issues:** The complexity of rules governing engagement between the EC and CSAs can lead to overstep and compliance challenges, potentially disrupting ongoing efforts and causing delays. Such bureaucratic complexities, including those around social media, who can talk to whom, etc., may hinder the project's ability to maximize its impact or even continue on its current trajectory of increasing engagement.
- **The left hand of the EC doesn’t know what the right hand is doing.** We saw this often with respect to social media. In addition to being unclear whether they could even “own” social media for the Mission, the graphics team at one point insisted we change the Twitter handle we created because it seemed too official and too linked to the EC, while the Secretariat later asked us via the MIP to rebrand all the channels to look more official and consistent. Legacy also became an issue later in the project as discussions ensued about whether the EC or their tender could in fact take over the accounts. This also posed problems as WP2 tried to give them ownership of one account but they repeatedly refused to provide the information necessary to take it over even though they requested the ownership to begin with. Internally, until they talk to each other and come up with solid rules over social media for such large initiatives, there will be issues in this arena. They cannot have a real expectation that all

partners can move forward in a consistent manner and in ways that please all EC parties as all EC parties are not in agreement on what they want or what should happen. This poses a serious threat to the Mission.

- **Web-Experience:** The Web Experience's long-term sustainability and relevance is dependent on resource availability. It is easy to update text content, but design and visual content changes need to be programmed. The complexity of providing content in multiple languages, especially when speakers prefer or insist on English, poses a significant challenge to effective communication and engagement. Dependence on specific technologies and service providers for Web Experience functionality and filming creates vulnerabilities and affects the Web Experience 's stability and performance.

Mission Ocean Digital Toolkit

Access here

<https://trello.com/b/Q2SEkijW/missionocean-social-media-toolkit>

Tracking link clicks.

bit.ly/MissionOceanSocialMedia

Total link clicks: 1,247

Image 11. The Trello Board serves as a central repository of communications tools and resources for project partners.

As an example of the legacy issues faced, the content from the Digital Academy was already recently moved to the Trello Board to ensure its availability beyond the end of the project as that website will no longer be available after May 15, 2025, due to cost. However, that also was not a long-term solution as the Trello board will no longer be updated after PREP4BLUE ends. So, WP2 has worked with the MIP to migrate all of the information on it to their platforms to ensure the content remains available through the MIP's longer term (ending in Dec. 2027). The same issues plague the social media channels and will again face the MIP once their contract ends. Until the EC decides to actively manage such channels, there will always be a risk they'll be lost.

5 Recommendations

Based on our analysis of the survey results, social media and Web Experience findings, other observations and work (including this SWOT analysis), and most importantly, WP2's boots-on-the-ground exposure to the in-and-outs of communicating the Mission and working with the numerous partners to do the same, WP2 recommends the Mission make some changes to the current protocols. We believe these changes would be, in most cases, easy to implement but could make huge impacts in terms of reach and engagement as well as efficiency with respect to time and cost savings.

WP2 recommendations include:

- **Have a dedicated and centralized communications/PR team or project specifically for reaching the broader public rather than relying on project partners** - Because the majority of the partners reach is often an echo chamber of other partners with limited access to the public, communication and media attempts at reaching the public should be more concentrated, collaborative, and facilitated through a common core team that are experts in such specific campaigning. Essentially, the Mission needs an official PR team if it hopes to actually reach the public and have “all of Europe understand their relationship with the waters in their backyards”. One work package per project dedicated to “citizen engagement” is not going to have the same results as a major agency that specializes in significant campaigns, which the Mission is.
- **Establish mandatory attendance and participation in the Communications Collaborative for all project partners** - While WP2 has facilitated extensive networking through in-person and virtual meetings and events, the most successful has been the Communications Collaborative which includes representatives from the CSAs, projects, the EC, and others. Attendance could be made mandatory, and the group could be expanded to play a larger role in facilitating coherent social media, website, and other content sharing/exposure. Indeed, the Communications Collaborative monthly meetings are instrumental in ensuring all communications partners have a direct line to the EC and can get the questions they have answered and the products they need developed.
- **Select at least two mandatory social media channels that all projects must use daily** – Social media has connected many partners and engaged a wider public and these platforms continue to grow. However, the current political climate makes assessing which platforms to use difficult. Moreover, social media channels reach very different demographics, and it's important to select ones that will reach the right audiences. We believe projects should be mandated to use at least two common platforms, *e.g.*, LinkedIn and Instagram/TikTok to ensure everyone has at least a chance to get the messaging being promoted. While the EC may not support TikTok, the fact is that platform is where the younger generation is consuming content. Moreover, using at least two common platforms presents a unified front in terms of everyone knowing that all Mission Ocean project information can always be found on those two platforms.
 - Additionally, a centralized social media team to collect and distribute information via those main platforms on a regular basis (daily at a minimum) would better ensure information reaches relevant stakeholders in a more timely and consistent fashion. Individual projects working on several tasks and deliverables, and the MIP, simply don't have the time or resources to effectively manage all social media for the entire Mission and all its projects. This requires a dedicated team whose sole job is social media and communicating the Mission to the public and partners.

- **Have one, and only one, centralized website for everything, including the projects** – The Web Experience offers a storytelling perspective on the Mission, which complements the EC site and MIP Service Portal. However, there are many dozens of websites at central and project levels all adding levels of redundancy. There is no way the public nor the partners are reviewing all of the websites to gather information; there are simply too many. The Mission should have one website with everything for everyone, including a more accessible list of the projects and what they do. Projects should simply provide content to that main site so stakeholders and the public could easily access everything. Too many “one-stop-shops” have been created, resulting in not a single legitimate one-stop-shop existing. And the time, money, and resources that go into each project creating their own website is wasteful given that one website would better facilitate information sharing and gathering both for partners and the public. Dynamic content such as the Web Experience could be incorporated.
- **The MIP, or other such entity, is integral to facilitating collaboration and information sharing between projects and the EC, and they need to remain an active part of the Mission** – The MIP as a nexus of communication has been successful throughout this project. However, the complexity of EU processes and legal gray areas continues to be a challenge. In the event these legal issues can’t be resolved in terms of the EU communicating with the partners, the MIP should continue to be a central player facilitating communications and community building.
- **Large-scale events targeting the public require a dedicated team, large budget, and accessible resources** – WP2 was tasked with organizing events. V.ECOP Days has been a success; however, organizing events is time-consuming and resource intensive. The vast numbers of events being held regionally and Europe-wide without clear coordination means that making time and financial commitments comes with substantial risks. If public engagement on a wide scale is expected, then much more strategic planning as well as a focused budget and resources need to be available and coordinated. Again, a dedicated, professional, experienced PR team that focuses solely on reaching the public is necessary for something as large as the Mission.
- **Clarify legal grey areas at the EC, especially with respect to communicating directly with projects and regarding official social media channels for the Mission** – PREP4BLUE and the CSAs encountered a number of problems at the start of the project in terms of communicating directly with the EC teams responsible for branding and social media. Partners expressed frustration related to getting adequate and timely answers and necessary resources, such as officially branded posters for events, from the EC. WP2 was given completely contradictory instructions regarding social media accounts and branding at different times in the project. Our understanding is this was largely related to complicated legal issues, and for that reason, we strongly recommend these are dealt with before larger problems ensue, such as the complete loss of the social media accounts after building them up to nearly ten thousand followers.
- **Stop reinventing the wheel and look closely at what the project calls are asking for and doing after funding** – Duplicative efforts across the EC with projects, CSAs, and PREP4BLUE seem to be an obvious waste of time, energy, and money. However, it seems that they happen a lot. For example, our proposal noted we’d complete the Communication Strategy. However, at the start of the project, it became clear that the EC had already contracted for one for the Mission. It was several hundred pages and very comprehensive, yet it was never used and WP2 created a new one for Mission Ocean and Waters. Multiple databases exist for networking, rather than one comprehensive one. Multiple reports on various subjects exist, but they keep being produced and saying much of the same. It would serve the Mission better to focus on creating new and innovative products and services that would actually help partners and projects make a meaningful boots-on-the-ground

contribution to the Mission that could actually be measured in terms of reducing pollution and making our ocean and waters healthier. Another report on subjects that have been covered by multiple projects and only restate the obvious is not helping in the way other products and services could. The EC needs to take a much closer look at what they're asking for in each call and how many projects are doing the exact same thing.

- **Have reasonable expectations** – Several lines were blurred for WP2 in terms of existing as a CSA while being treated like a tender from “challenging” personalities at the EC. This was especially true with respect to conflicting social media requests as well as excessive requests for attendance at events. Expectations need to match reality as well as the grant agreement.
- **Exploit the resources that are performing and reconsider things that show low engagement** – Regular evaluations of product performance could help the projects better understand what is working and what isn't, allowing them to readjust priorities. In our case, it seems the Narrative Guide and Communications Strategy weren't nearly as effective or helpful as the Trello Board and monthly Communications Collaborative meetings in terms of facilitating effective communication, information sharing, and adherence to brand guidelines. An example might include asking the questions “why is every project creating a communication strategy and website when the Mission has its own ideas for what it wants?” or “why can't the projects use the resources that already exist to save time and money?” or “how many project partners are reading or even adhering to their own communication strategy?”

6 Conclusion

This SWOT analysis demonstrates that WP2 has successfully delivered on the commitments (tasks and deliverables) outlined in the grant agreement. This is despite challenges related to the complexity of the EU Mission Ocean and Waters, the complexity of EU processes and rules, sustainability and legacy gaps, content/task overlap, influence on the initial direction of the communications (branding), excessive requests involving staff time and extra costs, *etc.* WP2 adjusted as needed and demonstrated strengths in engagement, strategic communication, and collaborative networking, particularly through consistent collaboration with multiple partners, the production of multiple tools and resources, events targeting ECOPs (a key audience) and art, and impactful social media growth through content and campaigns.

Each strength, weakness, opportunity, and threat demonstrate that there is both room for improvement as well as successes that can be translated across the Mission well into the future. The opportunities identified provide a path forward for leveraging the strengths and addressing the weaknesses to ensure continued success and impact. Utilizing the established networks and continuing to engage with new and diverse stakeholders will be crucial moving forward.

7 ANNEX

Mission Ocean and Waters: Social Media Report	33
Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment - Full Report, Including Individual Survey Responses	43

7.1 Mission Ocean and Waters: Social Media Report

Funded by the European Union,
through its Horizon Europe Programme,
Grant No.101056957 (PREP4BLUE).

PREP4BLUE
METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

DIGITAL
Training
Institute

**EU
MISSIONS**

RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS

Final Social Media Report for Mission Ocean

Period:

1 June 2022 – 12 May 2025

Prepared by:

Joanne Sweeney, Digital Training Institute
and Wendy Namisnik, KDM

Table of contents

Executive Summary [3](#)

SWOT Analysis [4](#)

Social Media Footprint at End of Project [6](#)

Additional Strategic Insight [6](#)

Mission Ocean Digital Academy [8](#)

Mission Ocean Digital Toolkit [9](#)

Executive Summary

Between June 2022 and May 2025, the Mission Ocean social media channels established a strong digital presence across six platforms: Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, X, YouTube and TikTok publishing over 3,000 posts and generating more than 20,000 engagements and 2.1 million impressions. We experimented with Pinterest but it didn't deliver a return and the results were negligible.

The social media strategy successfully tailored content for diverse audiences, from EU citizens and youth to policymakers and scientific communities. Instagram and X were the most active and engaging channels initially, however, LinkedIn emerged as the most effective for professional and policy-related reach, especially in the final year.

TikTok showed promise for storytelling but struggled with audience growth as human-led content works best there. Strategic content such as original Lighthouse-specific case studies, event coverage, Horizon EU project features, and explainer content performed best, while partnerships with HorizonEU, European Commission accounts, and NGOs amplified visibility.

Insights from this final report provide valuable lessons on content planning, influencer activation, and platform prioritisation that can inform future EU mission communications.

SWOT Analysis

| <p>Weaknesses</p> |
|---|---|
| <p>✓ Strong, unified brand presence across all major platforms</p> | <p>⚠ Limited audience growth on Facebook and TikTok</p> |
| <p>✓ High LinkedIn reach and engagement among professionals and policymakers (estimated 597K impressions)</p> | <p>⚠ TikTok failed to develop a follower base</p> |
| <p>✓ X consistently active with high engagement (11.8K) and steady follower growth</p> | <p>⚠ Facebook engagement plateaued despite high volume of posts</p> |
| <p>✓ Content tied to events, island case studies, and MoJo stories performed well</p> | <p>⚠ LinkedIn underutilised in 2022–2023; most traction in final year</p> |
| <p>✓ Instagram Reels and campaign visuals drove solid impressions (107.9K)</p> | <p>⚠ Reducing X reach and engagement</p> |

SWOT Analysis

| <p>Threats</p> |
|---|--|
| <p> Platform algorithm changes reducing organic visibility</p> |
| <p> Limited internal resources to support content planning and video production</p> |
| <p> Audience fragmentation may require narrower targeting and paid boosts</p> |
| <p> Potential cuts to communications budgets post-project phase</p> |
| <p> Reputational risk on X right now</p> |

Social Media Footprint at End of Project

Platform	Followers	Total Posts	Total Engagement	Total Impressions
Facebook	1,272	703	1,987	53K
Instagram	1,061	459	4,159	108K
LinkedIn	5,218	389	1258	597k
X	2,043	2,045	12K	1.3m
TikTok	14	73	143	19.2K (views)
YouTube	25	62	1042	5,297 (views)
Total	12,802	3,731	20,589	2.1m

Additional Strategic Insight

1. Audience Insights

- Geographic Reach:**
 Strongest engagement came from Ireland, Belgium, France, Italy, and Germany, closely aligning with event locations and project partners.
- Demographics:**
 Predominantly 25–44 years old; slight female skew on Instagram, balanced on Facebook; LinkedIn skewed professional (policy, research, project leads).
- Languages:**
 Majority of engagement in English, with occasional local-language comments (notably Italian, French, Irish).
- Key Segments:**
 Policymakers, island/coastal communities, youth participants, NGOs, science communicators.

2. Content Themes That Performed Best

- **Top Themes:**
 - Personal testimonies from islands (e.g. Aran Islands, Chloe Ní Mhaílle)
 - Event storytelling (e.g. #EuropeanOceanDays, Palermo case study clips)
 - Explainer-style posts about ocean science and innovation
 - Mobile Journalist (MoJo) behind-the-scenes content and video diaries

3. Partnership & Amplification

- **Collaborations:**

Significant boosts from HorizonEU, EC Missions accounts, WWF, EU4Ocean, and institutional partners resharing content.
- **Cross-Tagging:**

Effective in increasing impressions on Twitter and Instagram.
- **Media Mentions:**

Select posts embedded in press releases and institutional newsletters.

4. Engagement Quality

- **Tone:**

Overall sentiment was positive, particularly around personal stories and youth engagement.
- **Community Responses:**

Audiences showed appreciation for authentic content; occasional policy questions were answered by project staff or partners.

5. Influencer & Ambassador Impact

- **Contributors:**

MoJos like Aakriti, Fiona, and Mariam brought credibility and relatability.
- **Tactics Used:**

TikTok and Instagram featured ambassador-led storytelling; live event coverage added value but had limited reach due to follower base size.

6. Content Planning Lessons

- **Efficiency vs Impact:**
 - Instagram Reels and X Threads delivered strong ROI vs effort.
 - LinkedIn posts, while infrequent, generated the highest stakeholder visibility.
- **Workflow Takeaways:**
 - Tools like scheduling dashboards (i.e. AgoraPulse), content calendars, and Canva templates streamlined collaboration.

7. Recommendations for Future EU Missions

- **Platform Focus:**

Prioritise Instagram (Reels), LinkedIn (policy comms), and X (campaigns); reassess TikTok viability.
- **Partnership Planning:**

Build resharing agreements into the project from the outset with DG RTD, EC campaigns, and NGOs.
- **KPI Suggestions:**
 - Engagement rate per post
 - Monthly active follower growth
 - Video completion rate (Reels/TikTok)
 - Partner amplification count
 - Sentiment score (quarterly)

Mission Ocean Digital Academy

Total Members: 468

Average Retention: 502 days

Average Progress: two tutorials completed on average per participant

Average Days To Complete: 7

Mission Ocean Digital Toolkit

Access here

<https://trello.com/b/Q2SEkkyW/missionocean-social-media-toolkit>

Tracking link clicks.

bit.ly/MissionOceanSocialMedia

Total link clicks: 1,247

7.2 Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment - Full Report, Including Individual Survey Responses

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment Report for D2.5 Annex

Deliverable leader: 4 - German Marine Research Consortium – KDM

Authors: Wendy Namisnik (KDM), Stefan Fritz (KDM)

Work package Leader: WP2 – KDM

Project founded by the European Commission within the HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO Confidential, only for member of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2022

www.Prepare4Blue.eu

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DISCLAIMER

“PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters” has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call *“Preparation for deployment of ‘lighthouse demonstrators’ and solution scale ups and cross-cutting citizen and stakeholder involvement (HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01)”*, Grant Agreement n° 101056957.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

MISSION OCEAN & WATERS: COMMUNICATION TOOLS & RESOURCES ASSESSMENT REPORT FOR D2.5 ANNEX	1
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS	5
1 INTRODUCTION	6
1.1 WP2 TOOLS & RESOURCES	6
2 COMMUNICATION TOOLS & RESOURCES ASSESSMENT	10
2.1 COMMUNICATION TOOLS & RESOURCES ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS.....	10
2.2 SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS	11
2.3 ILLUSTRATIVE GRAPHS OF YES/NO ANSWERS	13
2.4 ILLUSTRATIVE GRAPHS OF RANKINGS.....	17
2.5 RECOMMENDATIONS	20
3 NEXT STEPS.....	20
4 CONCLUSION	20
5 INDIVIDUAL SURVEY RESPONSES (24).....	21

TABLE OF FIGURES

TABLE 1. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS USED IN PREP4BLUE AND THE DOCUMENT	5
TABLE 2. TASKS, DELIVERABLES & OTHER PRODUCTS & SERVICES WP2 DEVELOPED & IMPLEMENTED FROM 2022 TO 2025.	6

Executive Summary

As the first CSA to both start and end, PREP4BLUE's Work Package (WP2) was responsible for creating a variety of communication tools and resources to support and aid project partners, including the four Lighthouse CSAs and other funded Mission Ocean and Waters projects, in their communication endeavors.

Toward the end of PREP4BLUE's contract, WP2 created the ["Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment"](#). The purpose of the survey was to assess the value of the communication tools and resources WP2 developed or provided that were meant to help partners in communicating the Mission and their project's role within it while adhering to brand guidelines. The survey was conducted among the Mission Ocean & Waters Communications Collaborative members, a group of CSA and project communications leaders who meet monthly to discuss ongoing communications issues and either address or hear from the EC on important communication issues. The Communications Collaborative group was itself started by WP2 as a communications resource. The survey was open from March through April 2025, and 24 responses were received.

This report evaluates the responses to the survey and provides key findings in summary and graph form. Areas assessed include the Trello Board, Web Experience, Digital Academy, social media, other documents, the Communications Collaborative working group meetings, and more.

Results reveal a strong appreciation for collaboration tools and resources but also note limited awareness or usability issues for certain platforms. Moving forward, WP2 recommends the Communication Collaborative monthly meetings continue, even without PREP4BLUE and the Lighthouse CSAs moderating them, that the EC centralize web and social media duties and platforms, and that the tools and resources developed continue to live on in accessible formats for all partners through legacy efforts, mostly managed by the MIP and EC.

As PREP4BLUE concludes its work, the survey confirms that WP2's communications efforts laid valuable groundwork and that continued investment in coordinated, accessible, and strategic communication will be critical to sustaining momentum and visibility for the Mission Ocean and Waters initiative across Europe and beyond.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
P4B	PREP4BLUE
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
the Mission	Mission Ocean and Waters
DX.X	Deliverable (by number)
WP2	Work Package 2 (within PREP4BLUE)
MIP	Mission Implementation Platform
EC	European Commission
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
KDM	Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung
DTI	Digital Training Institute

1 Introduction

PREP4BLUE's Work Package 2 (WP2) provided a number of tools, resources, and services as well as supported and attended multiple events that resulted in several mini-campaigns on social media – all of which were meant to enhance communication for Mission Ocean and Waters. Collectively, these products and activities supported Mission Lighthouse CSAs and project partners and enhanced overall communication, collaboration, and visibility of the Mission. However, measuring the level of usefulness is not an easy task, and ensuring the effectiveness of the tools, resources, and services is key to aiding the Mission in future endeavours, especially as PREP4BLUE and the four Lighthouse CSAs sunset.

Therefore, at the conclusion of the PREP4BLUE project, WP2 wanted to assess the perceived value that the tools, resources, and services added in the most efficient way possible. WP2 developed the survey, "[Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment](#)", and asked Mission Ocean and Waters partners who attend the Communications Collaborative meetings to complete it. Members of the Communications Collaborative are the primary communications leaders working for Mission Ocean and Waters projects who are invited to attend the "Comms Collab" monthly meetings to stay abreast of "all things communication" within the Mission, including hearing directly from the European Commission (EC).

The main purpose of the survey was to assess the value of the communication tools and resources WP2 developed or provided that were meant to help partners in communicating the Mission and their project's role within it while adhering to brand guidelines. Then, WP2 could reasonably make recommendations to be included in D2.5, a final SWOT analysis of their work, including with respect to "legacy plans".

The survey was open from March through April 2025, and 24 responses were received.

The sections below include information on the tools, resources, and services provided, a list of the survey questions, general findings, illustrative graphs and statistics, concluding thoughts and recommendations, and the individual survey responses.

Questions regarding the survey or this report should be addressed to Wendy Namisnik of KDM.

1.1 WP2 Tools & Resources

To understand the point of the survey, it's important to understand the characteristics of the tools, resources, and services provided. A list of WP2's outputs with descriptions and links to the item are in the table below. The majority of the items noted can also be found on the Trello Board at <https://trello.com/b/Q2SEkjyW/missionocean-social-media-toolkit>.

Table 2. Tasks, deliverables, and other products & services WP2 developed and implemented from 2022 to 2025

WP2 Tools & Resources - Descriptions & Links	
<p>✓ Narrative Guide (T2.1 & D2.1) https://trello.com/c/UrcREakR and doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944248</p>	<p>This guide was developed to facilitate storytelling about the Mission, fostering a sense of connection and empathy among the public. It was posted on the Trello Board for all partners to utilize in their media work, promoted in meetings, and elements are incorporated into the Web Experience and referenced in the Communication Strategy, which was also provided to all partners via the Trello Board.</p>
<p>✓ Communication Strategy (T2.2 and D2.2) https://trello.com/c/qcAyfDss and doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10944488</p>	<p>A cohesive communication strategy was devised to ensure consistent branding and enhance public recognition of the Mission. It's on the Trello Board for all partners to utilize in their media work.</p>
<p>✓ Report On Virtual Space Pilot and Website Including Overview of Existing Mission Contributions and Spaces for Mission-Related Events (D2.3) https://zenodo.org/records/10944310</p>	<p>This report summarized the development and implementation of the Web Experience and our events approximately half-way through the project.</p>
<p>✓ Interim SWOT Analysis of WP Product Implementation (D2.4) https://zenodo.org/records/14872535</p>	<p>Developed mid-term, this report summarized the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the development, implementation, and dissemination of WP2's products and services. The analysis was used to ensure the last half of the project remained in line with our goals and objectives.</p>
<p>✓ Final SWOT Analysis of WP Product Implementation (D2.5) (This Document)</p>	<p>This final deliverable report summarizes the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the development, implementation, and dissemination of WP2's products and services. More comprehensive than D2.4, it also includes two other reports WP2 produced that were used to make this final assessment; these reports collected data and feedback on social media and WP2's tools and resources' effectiveness. Data on the Web Experience was also collected. D2.5 also makes a number of recommendations based on the SWOT for the EC to consider as the Mission continues and evolves without PREP4BLUE.</p>
<p>✓ Web Experience (Subtask 2.3.2) Missionoceanwaters.eu</p>	<p>Designed to complement the EC's Mission webpage, this Web Experience features testimonials, interviews, and visually compelling content to capture the public's attention and engagement by showcasing Mission Lighthouses and individual contributions through immersive scenes. It's featured on the "One-Stop Shop Portal" accessed via the EC's Mission Ocean and Waters webpage.</p>

✓ **Social Media Channels (Task 2.2) & Campaigns (Subtask 2.3.1)**

Seven social media channels were created and four are regularly utilised to disseminate calls-to-action, event updates, videos, photos, and relevant information tailored to the target audience, including specialised campaigns. Several social media campaigns were held, including Lighthouse and other events to promote the Mission (often at the EC’s request) as well as our own “Generation Blue” campaign featuring original content from four mobile journalists (MoJos) to engage youth and change up the narrative for enhanced citizen engagement. Collectively, WP2 travelled to approximately 15 events across Europe to publicize the Mission live on social media. Partners were encouraged to email WP2 and the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP) with content they wanted published. The MIP has assumed a contributory role in posting on the channels (at the EC’s request), and part of the legacy plan is for them, or another tender or the EC, to take over the majority of posting when PREP4BLUE sunsets. A legacy plan was sent to PREP4BLUE’s project officer for consideration in consultation with the EC and MIP but as of the writing of this report, there was no response.

Channels include:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/missionoceaneu>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/ourmissionocean>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/missionocean/>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/missionoceaneu/>
- TikTok: <https://www.tiktok.com/missionoceanwaters>
- Pinterest: <http://pinterest.com/missionoceanwaters/>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC8Zj11TyDAUuDO8QNLnd9zw>

✓ **STARTS4WATER ARTS RESIDENCY & EXHIBITION (Subtask 2.3.3) <https://starts.eu/what-we-do/lighthouses-2/>**

WP2 collaborated with the STARTS4WATER project (Grant agreement ID: 101059372) to co-host and co-organize public events, exhibitions, etc. STARTS4WATER has an arts focus and WP2 collaborated to select artists-in-residence, provide a link between scientists and artists, and ultimately support the START4WATERS’ focus on the Mission Ocean and Waters goals. A date has not been set for the final conference, but it is expected to be in Brussels.

✓ **V.ECOP Days 2024, 2025 (Subtask 2.3.3) <https://vecop.net>**

The Virtual Early Career Ocean Professional (V.ECOP) Days are a unique livestream event series showcasing testimonies of change in applying science and knowledge to ocean sustainability from the global community of ECOPs. Hosted by and for ECOPs as a contribution to the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, on-site ECOP mobile journalists provided live coverage to showcase commitments to both the Decade and the Mission in Barcelona in 2024. This hybrid event attracted over 400 participants and over 100 live programme contributions from Europe and around the world. V.ECOP Days 2025 is planned for Nice in June 2025 as part of the UN Ocean Conference. Therefore, reporting on it for this report is not possible, but WP2 staff are involved in ensuring the event promotes the Mission.

✓ **“Communications Collaborative” Working Group (Bonus)**

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TU-o99gU_xxk1ALE4ggmn1z-ne4eGjif_fOvhU-y-el/edit?tab=t.0

This platform facilitates collaboration among Mission communication partners as described above. While started by WP2, the group was eventually handed over to the MIP to avoid duplicative efforts. It has continued to grow over the three years of the PREP4BLUE project, and 50-75 participants regularly attend the monthly meetings. Partners are invited by the MIP to join the group during their onboarding to the Mission and can also email MIP Communication at mip-communication@technopolis-group.com for more information.

✓ **Trello Board (Bonus)** <https://bit.ly/MissionOceanSocialMedia>

A comprehensive Trello Board (Trello.com is an online tool for sharing resources) serves as a centralised repository of communication information, tools, resources, and links related to the Mission, facilitating accessibility and dissemination of information to the partners and public. To ensure the content isn't lost, the MIP is working on migrating the content to their platforms.

✓ **PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit (Bonus)** <https://trello.com/c/Adz09TaT>

This toolkit, available in PDF format, was produced at the EC's request to complement the Trello Board. It serves as a resource for new projects, equipping them with the necessary information and materials to promote the Mission effectively. It is available on the Trello Board and also emailed to new partners by the MIP during onboarding.

✓ **Mission Ocean & Waters Digital Academy (Bonus)** <https://bit.ly/MissionOceanSocialMedia>

Previously an exclusive platform for project partners and charter signatories, the Academy was established to provide special communication tools and training on utilizing social media. The goal was to help the partners and signatories learn how to properly promote the Mission and their respective roles within it. While it was advertised as a bonus for Charter signatories and partners only, the content from the Academy was moved from its old platform to the publicly available Trello Board in March 2025 so the content isn't lost when PREP4BLUE ends in May 2025. The MIP is now working on moving the content to their platforms.

✓ **Events, Activities, & Meetings Attended to Foster Collaboration and Promote the Mission via Social Media (Bonus)**

WP2 staff attended in person approximately 15 Mission Ocean and Waters events, activities, or large meetings; these included all 3 Mission Ocean and Waters Forums, PREP4BLUE Annual Meetings, and Lighthouse or other related events in Marseille, Nice, Palermo, Gothenburg, Hamburg, Brussels, Barcelona, Brest, Genoa, Venice, Ravenna, Cork, Lisbon, and more. All events were promoted on social media channels via mini campaigns and can be viewed in past posts.

Image 1. The Trello Board serves as a central repository of communications tools and resources for project partners.

2 Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

2.1 Communication Tools & Resources Assessment Questions

The Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment included the following questions:

1. Have you visited the Trello Board (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?
2. Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.
3. How would you rate the Trello Board?
4. Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?
5. What was your impression of it?
6. How would you rate the Web Experience?
7. Have you visited the Digital Academy?
8. Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.
9. How would you rate the Digital Academy?
10. Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?
11. Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.
12. How would you rate the meetings?
13. Did you read the Narrative Guide, PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy, and/or PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners (all available on the Trello Board)? Check all that you've read.
14. How would you rate the Narrative Guide?
15. How would you rate the Communication Strategy?
16. How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?
17. Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC? Why or why not?
18. Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?
19. Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.
20. Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?
21. Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project?
22. Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.
23. Should we delete our X/Twitter account?
24. Should we create a Bluesky account?
25. Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?
26. Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24? If yes, what was your impression of it?
27. Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists? If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

28. Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.
29. Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

2.2 Summary of Key Findings

The [“Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment” survey](#) was conducted among the Mission Ocean & Waters Communications Collaborative members. The purpose of the survey was to assess the value of the communication tools and resources WP2 developed or provided that were meant to help partners in communicating the Mission and their project's role within it while adhering to brand guidelines. The survey was open from March through April 2025, and 24 responses were received. A brief synopsis of the key findings is below. Refer to the Annex for the full survey report, including copies of the 24 individual responses.

Summary of Key Findings:

The Mission Ocean and Waters communications tools and resources were generally well received by the 24 survey respondents, though many questions were left blank, making it difficult to ascertain true opinions on certain products from all project partner members of the group. Responses to open-ended questions demonstrated that while the tools and resources were viewed as useful overall, the main challenges were awareness gaps, onboarding inconsistencies, and occasional technical or navigational issues. Participants emphasized the strategic value of communication platforms in enhancing Mission visibility and coordination. Improving promotion and access to these resources—and strengthening the support for social media amplification—would enhance their impact moving forward. This is part of the reason WP2 recommends creating one centralized website for all projects, partners, and information as well as establishing mandatory/main social media platforms.

General findings include:

Web-Based Resources:

- **Trello Board (Social Media Toolkit):** Most respondents were aware of and had used the Trello Board, finding it valuable for accessing branded content and staying updated. However, a few found its layout overwhelming or had not had time to explore it fully. It was visited more than 1200 times using the tracking link; however there were other links users could have used, meaning it could have been visited even more.
- **Mission Web Experience (missionoceanwaters.eu):** Feedback on the site's design was mostly positive, with users appreciating the creative and immersive aspects. However, there were reports of usability issues, bugs, and slow performance - limiting its effectiveness.
- **Digital Academy:** Some users had trouble accessing the platform or were unaware of it altogether. 17 respondents opted not to rate it. Those who did access it found it average to below-average. This suggests that it may not have been worth the effort. However, based on usage statistics, 468 people registered to use it and on average watched two videos.

Meetings & Collaboration:

- **Communications Collaborative Working Group Meetings:** These were generally viewed as very beneficial, particularly for staying informed and collaborating across projects. Only a few respondents were unaware of the meetings, and this illustrates how important consistent outreach during onboarding is. Respondents appreciated updates from the European Commission and opportunities for networking and synergy among projects. 15 out of 24 respondents rated them highly. The other 9 didn't respond. There were no negative ratings, suggesting this is one of the most effective tools at the Mission's disposal.

Strategic Tools:

- Tools like the **Narrative Guide, Communication Strategy, and PREP4BLUE Toolkit** were sometimes read and rated positively, although several participants were unaware of their existence or had not engaged with them.
- Lack of knowledge about the **CIRCABC Group** (managed by the EC and used to access official media resources not available on the Trello board) was common. This platform is not managed by WP2.

Social Media Usage & Preferences:

- **LinkedIn** emerged as the most useful platform for professional engagement and updates among partners in the group. **Twitter/X** drew mixed reactions, with some supporting its removal and others still using it; it remains the platform with our second largest group of followers amongst partners. There was support for a BlueSky account.
- There was limited to moderate awareness of the **Generation Blue** and **V.ECOP Days 24** campaigns. Participants appreciated youth engagement but felt more project-centered amplification was needed. These results may also be due in part to some of the respondents having started their projects after these events took place.

Image 2. The majority of partners follow the accounts on LinkedIn and X, although some think the X account should be deleted in favour of BlueSky.

2.3 Illustrative Graphs of Yes/No Answers

The graphs below illustrate answers to the yes/no questions from the assessment. Answers to questions that were open-ended and resulted in written comments can be found in the individual survey responses in [Section 5](#).

Image 3. 19 out of 24 respondents have visited the Trello Board.

Image 4. 18 out of 24 respondents have visited the Web Experience.

Image 5. The majority of respondents have not visited the Digital Academy. This may be due to the fact they are already the communications leaders and don't need instruction, and/or because they aren't targeted as "charter signatories" but rather project partners.

Image 6. The majority of respondents attend or have a partner that attends the Communications Collaborative meetings.

Image 7. Results are fairly evenly split on whether the X account should be deleted.

Image 8. More than half of respondents agree a BlueSky account should be created.

Image 9. 20 out of 24 respondents had not accessed the CIRCABC group managed by the EC.

Image 10. The majority of partners do not recall hearing about V.ECOP Days 2024. This could be attributed to them having started their projects after the event.

Image 11. The majority of partners do not recall hearing about the Generation Blue campaign. This could be attributed to them having started their projects after the event.

2.4 Illustrative Graphs of Rankings

Image 12. Half of respondents rated the Trello board highly. One quarter didn't answer and one quarter rated it moderate to low.

Image 13. 10 respondents rated the Web Experience highly. One quarter didn't answer and one third rated it moderate to low.

Image 14. 15 out of 24 respondents rated the Communications Collaborative meetings highly. Nine didn't answer. No one rated it low.

Image 15. 17 out of 24 respondents didn't rate the Digital Academy. The remaining seven rated it moderate to low.

Image 16. Half of the respondents didn't answer this question. One third rated the PDF Toolkit highly. The remaining rated it moderate to low.

Image 17. 13 respondents didn't answer the question. One quarter rated the Narrative Guide highly and the remaining rated it moderate to low.

Image 17. 12 out of 24 respondents didn't answer the question. 8 rated it highly. The remaining four rated it moderate to low.

2.5 Recommendations

Overall, the tools developed by WP2 served as foundational communication infrastructure for the Mission. Yet, to ensure their lasting impact and scalability, the following recommendations are strongly encouraged:

- Maintain and expand the Communications Collaborative meetings, even after PREP4BLUE concludes, ideally with MIP and other leading projects taking the reins.
- Centralize communication resources—including onboarding, toolkits, and access portals—on a single, user-friendly platform to reduce confusion and enhance usability.
- Continue legacy support and visibility for the most-used tools, particularly the Trello Board, Web Experience, and other content.
- Improve onboarding processes to ensure all partners are systematically informed of available resources, including lesser-known platforms.
- Strengthen social media amplification efforts, particularly via LinkedIn and other high-engagement platforms, while reevaluating channels such as Twitter/X and BlueSky. Deciding who the key audience is for each platform is imperative, especially as the need for more public engagement increases.

3 Next Steps

WP2 and the MIP are working together to ensure all resources created by WP2 as well as other resources that have been added to the Trello Board over time are migrated to MIP platforms before PREP4BLUE ends on May 31, 2025. There is a tentative plan in place for social media where the MIP will continue to manage the main social media posting and acquire full administrative rights. Additionally, Wendy Namisnik (KDM, WP2 Lead) will remain an active contributor and administrator through her role on another Mission Ocean and Waters project (TIDAL ArtS). Finally, between May 31, 2025, and December 2026 when the MIP's tender ends, the MIP and the EC will work out the next steps and Wendy will be able to remove herself as owner of the accounts. That plan has not been approved by the EC as of the time of publishing this report.

4 Conclusion

The results of the Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment underscore the significant progress made by WP2 in creating and deploying a diverse suite of communication tools and platforms that have, overall, been appreciated and utilized by project partners. Notably, the Trello Board, Web Experience, and the Communications Collaborative monthly meetings emerged as the most well-known and valued tools, contributing to better information flow, branding consistency, and enhanced cross-project coordination.

However, the survey responses also reveal persistent challenges that hinder the full potential of these tools—namely, uneven awareness, accessibility barriers, and fragmented onboarding processes. For example, despite the strategic value of the Digital Academy, many users were either unaware of it or faced access issues, limiting its reach and utility. Similarly, several respondents had never heard of the CIRCABC Group or key strategy documents, and others had joined the Communications Collaborative only through peer referral, highlighting critical information gaps during the onboarding phase.

Feedback on the Mission Ocean & Waters social media channels was similarly mixed. While LinkedIn was identified as the most effective channel for professional communication and engagement, usage and perceived value varied widely across other platforms. Suggestions from respondents included expanding visibility efforts, improving cross-promotion, and exploring emerging platforms such as BlueSky. The debate over whether to delete X continues.

As PREP4BLUE concludes its work, the survey confirms that WP2's communications efforts laid valuable groundwork. Continued investment in coordinated, accessible, and strategic communication will be critical to sustaining momentum and visibility for the Mission Ocean and Waters initiative across Europe and beyond.

5 Individual Survey Responses (24)

The 24 individual survey responses are below.

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

To easily access digital media content and branded material from the Mission.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

3

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

How would you rate the Web Experience?

3

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

3

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Both general communications and upcoming events are useful to be updated on PREPBLUE news in regards the Mission WG, to identify possible synergies and collaboration with other project actions and be aware of events and efforts carried out by relevant projects.

How would you rate the meetings?

5

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

4

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

3

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

4

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
- No

Why or why not?

Directly contacted to obtain branded materials for the Mission. Not aware of the CIRCABC Group.

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Linkedin as the platform to get informed and read on all information related to EU research & innovation.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Just recently joined the platform.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

This platforms are so necessary and useful, not only to amplify the mission impact, but to strategically align with other projects, provide a forum for discussion and better target actions and efforts based on shared information and knowledge

Thank you!

Contact

[Contact Form](#)

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
- No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

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Thank you!

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

n/a. I am aware of this tool, but so far, was too busy to start investigate the contents

How would you rate the Trello Board?

1

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

cannot say. I was not aware of this website

How would you rate the Web Experience?

0

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

cannot say. I was not aware of this website

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

1

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

all is OK

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

1

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

1

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

1

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

Yes

No

Why or why not?

never heard of

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.

I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.

I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.

I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.

I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.

I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.

I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.

Other - describe below.

Other

I didn't get informed about most of the tool. I am aware of the Trello board only because it was mentioned a few times at the monthly communication meetings

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

[Facebook](#)

[X/Twitter](#)

[LinkedIn](#)

[Instagram](#)

[TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

sorry, I don't like social media and follow only those which are for some reason mandatory, but I am not active at all

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

yes, particularly for our open call for associated regions, we got plenty of applications

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

I don't know, I am not involved in communication really much and am not an expert in this either

Thank you!

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

3

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

It is really amazing!

How would you rate the Web Experience?

4

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
- No

Why or why not?

There are so many groups and resources that it can get overwhelming at times. Especially, if Mission Ocean projects aren't the only ones we are involved in.

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

All which I follow.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

such information hasn't been distributed yet.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

I liked it.

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thank you!

Contact

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Information on visuals for the Mission, and the social media accounts of the projects

How would you rate the Trello Board?

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

It looks nice, but it's a shame all the information remain on the ec.europa website. I am not sure I undersand the point of the webpage.

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Other projects announcing events & calls

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
 I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
 I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
 I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
 I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn, as I don't use Instagram professionally. LinkedIn is my way of staying up to date for my job.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

I can find resources to repost or like via my project channels, for our followers

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thank you!

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[Contact Form](#)

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

We used some of the informative sections on the Trello Board. An example would be Service Portal, Newsletters, Helpdesks, Resources & Events. It is useful for identifying synergies and potential partners for the exchange of best practices for the SUNDANSE project and beyond. As well as for potential contacts to identify a consortium for future projects.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

We find interesting the idea of visualizing project teams in the environment in which they carry out their activity. The initiative could be extended by taking photos and images from several projects related to the missions and results obtained.

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

I tried to log in to Digital Academy but I didn't receive the email for the password.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
 I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
 I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
 I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
 I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Mission Ocean and Water develops multiple useful activities. Communication is an important part of these activities. The pragmatic section in which partners already active in the projects could propose new ideas related to Calls could be improved and partnerships could be defined right from the public debate stage.

Thank you!

Contact

[Contact Form](#)

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Yes, it is useful to have all information all one place with a clear structure

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

The design looks great but it is a bit difficult to find information

How would you rate the Web Experience?

2

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

It's especially useful to hear from the Mission and DGs, and focus on collaboration at the Mission's level.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

I don't know what is the CIRCABC Group

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
 I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
 I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
 I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
 I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

As the Communication WP leader, we had not received information about the Mission Communication Collaborative. We were informed by another project and requested to join

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Instagram and LinkedIn are the most helpful as these are our best performing accounts.
We would be happy to receive more support on YouTube as it is more difficult to increase our numbers there.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Yes, we send a lot of content by emails and the team was always helpful in spreading our news

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thanks for the support!

There was a lot of confusion early on regarding the Mission's visual identity and requirements but it seems a lot clearer now and the flow of information between projects and the Mission works well.

Thank you!

Contact

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Not for the moment, but I will check it again to make sure I am using the corresponding materials

How would you rate the Trello Board?

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Specially, when a representative of the EC is there to share main messages, for example someone from DG MARE.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

I did not know about it until reading this survey

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
 I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
 I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
 I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
 I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn, and even though not included BlueSky would be an interesting platform to consider

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

I think this part could be reinforced in the project' side and the platform

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

I think it would be interesting to highlight one project each month with a sort of blog or storyline

Thank you!

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

All of them.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

5

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

Wow!

How would you rate the Web Experience?

5

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

3

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

4

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

5

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

4

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

Yes

No

Why or why not?

I did not know they existed.

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.

I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.

I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.

I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.

I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.

I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.

I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.

Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

[Facebook](#)

[X/Twitter](#)

[LinkedIn](#)

[Instagram](#)

[TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

All except X/Twitter.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

I would need some analytics first.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

I think they nailed it.

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

As a communications lead for an EU-funded project under the Mission Ocean and Waters umbrella, I found the communication tools and resources provided both supportive and evolving. There is a clear effort to harmonise branding, visibility rules, and strategic messaging, which is particularly helpful for projects trying to maintain coherence across partners and platforms.

Thank you!

Contact

[Contact Form](#)

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

How would you rate the Web Experience?

4

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Exchange between projects and support with dissemination

How would you rate the meetings?

5

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

4

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

4

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

4

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

Yes

No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

TikTok

Section 5: Final Thoughts

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Thank you!

Contact

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

yes, but the way it is presented is very overwhelming

How would you rate the Trello Board?

2

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

it was nice, but stuck on loading at "Explore the mission"
I like that it's very creative and doesn't follow usual website norms, which is great
however it takes a long time to load everything. I click on a button and it takes a lot of time to have a reaction, so I'm not sure what I did or if it even worked
there are also some bugs. I entered the port and am clicking the information button (i) and it is showing me the plastic pirates for every button I press. the names of the people have the same design as the rest, so they look clickable

How would you rate the Web Experience?

2

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
 No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?

Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
 No
 Sometimes
 I don't, but someone from our project does.
 What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
 I read the Communication Strategy.
 I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.

What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

not sure what that is

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
 I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
 I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
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 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)

- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)
- [YouTube](#)
- [Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

linkedin and youtube. linkedin is th place for work related things, youtube is where you can watch past recordings
your tiktok link isnt working and pinterest just seems weird to have a presence there
facebook us dead

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

- Yes
- No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

- Yes
- No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

- Yes
- No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

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Thank you!

Contact

[Contact Form](#)

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Yes. Very well organized everything is well presented.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

Not connected to the Mission Lighthouse actual activities its serving more like a situation report and promotion of one part of the Europe, but is not connected to any solution upgrade in the mission project. The design of the web page is well thought and intreaging.

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Having direct way to get a instructions for the mission communication strategy. Which was helpfull since the EC make a lot of changes in how they want to present the Mission ocean communication materials.

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

4

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

Didn't know existed.

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
 I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
 I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
 I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
 I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

All of them.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

It was just a sharing of the event like OC from the project post.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thank you!

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

How would you rate the Web Experience?

4

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
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Other

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- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Linkedin

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
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- Other - describe below.

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- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

I feel a bit overwhelmed by the many offers shown on the Trello Board

How would you rate the Trello Board?

2

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

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- What are those?

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How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

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 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

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- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

How would you rate the Web Experience?

4

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

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How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

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 Other - describe below.

Other

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Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

Nice

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Update on each other's activities and events is helpful

How would you rate the meetings?

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

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 I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn, most complete information

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Yes, we are waiting for our Flag video to be disseminated.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

The Trello Board is is comprehensive and all resources and tolls are valuable

How would you rate the Trello Board?

5

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

I like very much the way the info is presented, it is very different from the average website.

How would you rate the Web Experience?

5

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Presentations from projects are a good way to learn what is happening in other projects. I liked the meeting when projects were presented on the FSTP Call experience; it was helpful for us to prepare our own calls.

How would you rate the meetings?

5

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

5

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

5

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

5

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
- No

Why or why not?

I wanted to include the mission logos on our project website

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn connects us to people interested in our project work, and the interaction has been good.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Useful documents and Branded graphics/guidelines sections

How would you rate the Trello Board?

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

captivating but no clear mention to endorse the Mission Charter

How would you rate the Web Experience?

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

coordination among LH projects on calls, supporting programmes and events
sometimes the coordination with the EC is lacking

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
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- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

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- Other - describe below.

Other

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Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Mission Ocean channels should also serve as a platform to reshare other Mission projects activities and communications. although tags are regularly done, more often the posts are not reshared and not even liked.

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thank you!

Contact

[Contact Form](#)

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

The Important Links and Documents are very useful.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

Interactive, good.

How would you rate the Web Experience?

4

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

3

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

The meeting in general is helpful

How would you rate the meetings?

5

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

4

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

4

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

3

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

Yes

No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn. I use it regularly in my job so is easy to follow.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Yes

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thank you!

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Yes, great place to get logos, guidelines and see examples of social media.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

5

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

beautiful visually appealing website

How would you rate the Web Experience?

5

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

I did not know this existed

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

to be informed of campaigns, webinars, calls, branding issues etc.

How would you rate the meetings?

5

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

2

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

4

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

4

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

Yes

No

Why or why not?

did not know it existed

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn because it is more business oriented and more information can be supplied. I also find webinars useful.

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Yes very helpful in helping with the dissemination of our events and findings

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

PREP4BLUE along with the CSAs were great vehicles by which regional, national and local projects could find out and join the Communication group to share about their projects and to also meet with MIP and on occasion the Commission. It helped spread dissemination, uptake and a concerted joined up messaging. MIP and PREP4Blue were great in helping create so many useful resources and help the MO projects gain understanding of EC & MO branding guidelines.

Thank you!

Contact

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Yes I regularly visited the Trello board to find various elements of the visual identity.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

4

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

In general, I did not find very much helpful information for my work here, however, I have a very high level of knowledge on Mission Ocean so it may be more useful for people looking to find out initial information about the Mission

How would you rate the Web Experience?

3

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

3

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

I think it's helpful to hear updates from all of the projects and get an idea of what is going on within the world of Mission Ocean

How would you rate the meetings?

5

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

3

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

4

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

4

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

Yes

No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.

I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.

I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.

I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.

I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.

I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.

I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.

Other - describe below.

Other

I joined my project in the middle so this question does not apply to me

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

[Facebook](#)

[X/Twitter](#)

[LinkedIn](#)

[Instagram](#)

[TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

I personally find most information through LinkedIn, because the posts there have a lot of details and I use this platform most in my personal life

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Yes, I always found it easy to get my content featured on Mission Ocean platforms

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thank you!

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Yes, in particular the sections on important links, useful documents and branded graphics and guidelines

How would you rate the Trello Board?

5

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

Very nice website for the general public, really makes you want to learn more about the Mission Ocean & Waters and related themes and get active in the field. Perfect to raise awareness. From a Mission project perspective, the structure of the website is not so clear and it is not so good to inform about whats really going on in Mission projects - but I believe this is not the purpose of it

How would you rate the Web Experience?

4

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

I havent heard about the Digital Academy and was not aware it exists

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

They are great to get an impression what other projects are doing, get inspired and get your own project work more widely promoted/disseminated. Since there are always a lot of topics on the agenda, it was hard to really get into discussions on common problems/communication strategies/etc. - that would have also been nice and helpful

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
- No

Why or why not?

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)

- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)
- [YouTube](#)
- [Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

LinkedIn as I am involved in the Mission in my profession

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Yes, once distribution of information was requested, it was usually shared and helped spreading projects messages

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

- Yes
- No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

- Yes
- No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

- Yes
- No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

The involvement of young MoJos was mentioned several times and I expected a bit more to be honest. I only saw very few content of them

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

I was involved in the Mission from the beginning and still had troubles to have and keep an overview of all materials/channels available (PREP4BLUE deliverables, Trello board, Teams,). I imagine it even harder for projects that were later funded or colleagues that joined later on. A better overview of everything would be helpful

Thank you!

[Contact Form](#)

Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

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Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

Not really, the information on Trello were very confusing

How would you rate the Trello Board?

1

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

The website looks great! Very creative and interactive

How would you rate the Web Experience?

5

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

3

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

Communication with other Mission Ocean project's communication partners, updates on their work, collaboration, supporting each other's efforts

How would you rate the meetings?

5

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

1

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

1

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

1

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

- Yes
 No

Why or why not?

To get additional information besides what was already available on the Trello board, but the information available on CIRCABC was pretty much the same as in the Trello board.

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
 I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
 I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
 I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
 I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
 I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
 I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
 Other - describe below.

Other

Information was fragmented, inaccessible and confusing. A lot of effort was required on our end to follow up with all the information and documents shared and keep up with everything without things falling through the cracks

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
 [X/Twitter](#)
 [LinkedIn](#)
 [Instagram](#)
 [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Facebook. It's the most active one

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Yes, they were very helpful in disseminating our work and amplifying our reach

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

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As mentioned above, the information shared was fragmented and confusing in terms of who to contact about what, how to use the Mission's visual identity and how to access the visual identity elements. We appreciate the effort and the support to our project, but better organisation would be appreciated.

Thank you!

Contact

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Mission Ocean & Waters: Communication Tools & Resources Assessment

This survey will help us assess the value of the communication tools and resources we provided that were meant to help you in communicating the Mission and your project's role within it.

Section 1: Websites & the Web Experience

Have you visited the [Trello Board](#) (also known as the Mission Ocean Social Media Toolkit)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools on the Trello Board valuable to you in your work for the Mission? Please describe.

No, resources are difficult to find, documentation and material not directly ready to download.

How would you rate the Trello Board?

2

Have you visited the Web Experience at <https://missionoceanwaters.eu>?

- Yes
- No

What was your impression of it?

Interesting presentation about the goals and figures regarding objectives. However, Difficult to understand why there's a project featured but not all? Who is this people talking? There's no specific user journey on the website, there's no clear journey for the visitor.

How would you rate the Web Experience?

1

Have you visited the [Digital Academy](#)?

- Yes
- No

Were any of the resources/tools in the Digital Academy valuable to you in your work for the Mission?
Please describe.

I'm not aware of what or where is it, so I'm not gonna rate next question.

How would you rate the Digital Academy?

3

Section 2: Communications Collaborative Working Group Monthly Meetings

Do you attend the monthly Communications Collaborative working group meetings hosted by the MIP, PREP4BLUE, and Lighthouse CSAs?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes
- I don't, but someone from our project does.
- What are the Communications Collaborative meetings?

Which parts of the meetings are helpful/not helpful? Please describe.

All are great. I think communication guidelines should be repeated or reminded, at least documentation, in all meetings or minutes, as in every meeting there's someone new.

How would you rate the meetings?

4

Section 3: Other Tools & Resources

Did you read the [Narrative Guide](#), [PREP4BLUE Mission Ocean Communication Strategy](#), and/or [PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners](#) (all available on the Trello Board)?

Check all that you've read.

- I read the Narrative Guide.
- I read the Communication Strategy.
- I read the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I didn't read them, but I'm aware of them.
- What are those?

How would you rate the Narrative Guide?

2

How would you rate the Communication Strategy?

2

How would you rate the PREP4BLUE Communication Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners?

2

Have you accessed the private CIRCABC Group to get Mission Ocean and Waters official media resources from the EC?

Yes

No

Why or why not?

I'm not sure, what is CIRCABC

Did you receive information about all of the tools and resources available to you when you joined the Mission, for example through the MIP?

- I received the PREP4BLUE Communications Toolkit for Mission Ocean and Waters Partners.
- I was invited to the monthly Communications Collaborative meetings.
- I was informed about the Trello Board for information and resources.
- I learned about the [Web Experience](#) and other helpful websites.
- I learned about the Digital Academy and was told how to gain access.
- I was informed about the MIP Service Portal and EC webpage for the Mission.
- I was given information on all the social media channels and asked to submit my project's social media information for the master list.
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 4: Social Media

Which Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels do you follow? Check all that apply.

- [Facebook](#)
- [X/Twitter](#)
- [LinkedIn](#)
- [Instagram](#)
- [TikTok](#)

[YouTube](#)

[Pinterest](#)

Which platforms do you find the most helpful and why?

Linkedin and Instagram is where we have more followers and less hate

Do you feel that the Mission Ocean and Waters platforms were helpful in distributing information you needed shared and amplified for your project? Describe how these accounts helped your project, or any issues you encountered.

Not always, even if we tag to every post, we very rarely have a return from the Mission channels

Should we delete our X/Twitter account?

Yes

No

Should we create a Bluesky account?

Yes

No

Do you remember reading about Virtual Early Career Ocean Professionals Days 24 (V.ECOP Days 24) on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels?

Yes

No

Did you attend V.ECOP Days 24?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of it?

Do you remember the Generation Blue social media campaign that ran on the Mission Ocean and Waters social media channels and featured ECOPs as well as other youth-focused content captured by young mobile journalists?

Yes

No

If yes, what was your impression of that campaign?

Which social media channels do you use for your Mission Ocean and Waters project? Check all that apply.

- X/Twitter
- Facebook
- Instagram
- YouTube
- Bluesky
- Pinterest
- Mastadon
- LinkedIn
- Other - describe below.

Other

Section 5: Final Thoughts

Here you can provide any additional thoughts about the communication tools and resources available to you as part of Mission Ocean and Waters. These thoughts will be compiled and used to draw a final analysis that will be submitted to the European Commission as part of the final deliverable (D2.5: Final SWOT Analysis) by PREP4BLUE's WP2. No names or projects will be identified; your information will remain anonymous.

Thank you!

Contact

[Contact Form](#)